

Carella, K. *The Ideological Foundations of Early Irish Law and Their Reception in Anglo-Saxon England, c. 600 — c. 900*. Medieval Texts and Cultures of Northern Europe 37. Brepols Publishers. 2024 ISBN: 978-2-503-60731-3. 322 pages. €100.

The title of this monograph suggests something highly ambitious — the jurisprudential thoughts within the diverse body of early Irish legal writing, which include intriguing topics such as the nature of justice, the authority of written texts, the balance between hierarchy and equity, the role of analogy in the interpretation of law, the reason why Ireland was under a single jurisdiction, etc. While some of these topics have been touched upon in the book, the main jurisprudential idea analysed in the book is the interaction between the inherited native law and the imported Christian ideologies, and the place of the Irish people within the teleological sacred history (p. 13). Moreover, instead of analysing rules from the ‘operative’ law texts in order to reveal how the early Irishmen contemplated about justice and society, the author has focussed on the more abstract, ‘ideological’ sections in both secular and canon law, and at times on narratives and wisdom texts from the Old Irish period. Nonetheless, the author has put up many convincing arguments that are crucial to our understanding of early medieval Irish and Anglo-Saxon exegetic and legal ideologies. Regarding its theme and data, this monograph is aligned with recent significant contributions to the topic of medieval Irish intellectual history such as Lindy Brady’s *The Origin Legends of Early Medieval Britain and Ireland* (2022), Elizabeth Boyle’s *History and Salvation in Medieval Ireland* (2020), and Elva Johnston’s *Literacy and Identity in Early Medieval Ireland* (2013).

This focus on the outward-looking, theological sector in early Irish legal ideology is already apparent in Chapter 1, ‘Introduction’ (pp. 13–35), where the author has mostly preoccupied herself (pp. 16–35) on the letters of Columbanus to the Pope regarding the paschal controversy. In these letters, Columbanus has presented some interesting points such as that some legal (and theological) authorities should take precedence over others, including papal decrees (p. 19), and that the Irish people, as *exterae gentes*, may not be subject to the jurisdiction of Roman bishops on internal matters (p. 28). These ideas, revolutionary to the contemporaries on the Continent, are however pervasive and fundamental in early Irish legal writing.

Chapter 2, ‘Background’ (pp. 39–73), clarifies some of the terms the author uses, introduces the main argument and methodology, and reviews the primary documents examined in the book and relevant modern scholarship. The discussion on the use of ‘pre-Christian, native law’ and ‘ecclesiastical law’ is

valuable (pp. 39–40), although, I would argue, that the early Irish legal writing cannot be categorised along a single fault line. One may consider retaining Charles-Edwards' categorisation in *The Early Medieval Gaelic Lawyer*, quoted here on p. 40, which distinguishes the texts according to the language in which they were written (Latin vs. Irish), the purpose they serve (ecclesiastical vs. secular matters), and their ultimate origin (international vs. native). It is worth noting that by such a multi-dimensional categorisation, there is no one-to-one correspondence between a text and a category. A single paragraph can be a mixture of Latin and Irish, serve both ecclesiastical and secular purposes, and be a native rule modified by international ideas. More importantly, 'native' does not necessarily mean that it is 'pre-Christian': rules native to Ireland were still being formulated after Christianity was introduced, an example of which is the analogy of bees to cattle in regulations on bee-keeping, which may have been introduced into Ireland later than the arrival of Christianity. While I agree that the early Irish intellectual endeavour covered both law and theology, and even probably studied these texts with the same techniques, it may be a bit arbitrary to say that 'what we think of now as the separate fields of law and theology were conceived as one intellectual category in early medieval Ireland operating together, not conjointly but identically, in a single, unified gesture with the same goal(s)' (p. 41). I find it hard to imagine, when Irish jurists were busy calculating the proportions of inheritance given to each category of sons and nephews, what theological arguments and goals they had in mind. The author is no doubt right that the legal texts must be produced in a *scriptorium* milieu and under an overarching Christian framework (pp. 66–67). However, the ideological foundations underlying a large part of early Irish law, in the abovementioned case a concentric and patrilinear social structure imaginable in numerical terms, may not be covered under the 'legal-theological' perspective that the author adopts. I only say this because the author has eloquently demonstrated the importance of the Irish adaptation of the Christian ideological frameworks in the medieval conception of Irish law, whereas I would like to remind the readers that there are many other ideological foundations, not as theological but perhaps equally important, that underly medieval Irish jurisprudence.

Now, let us follow the author on the core questions: how did the Irish imagine themselves in terms of biblical history? And how did they reconcile their law into a cosmos where a series of other laws and authorities are also in operation? Chapter 3, 'Biblical law' (pp. 75–120), begins by reviewing the decision of the 'Synod of Jerusalem', summarised in Acts 15, which has huge implications for newly converted communities in establishing the appropriate application of biblical law (p. 76). Central to Acts 15 is 'a basic dispute in biblical law, in this case: what is the relationship between the Old Law of Moses and the New Law of Christ?' (p. 77). Other biblical sources that may have inspired the early Irish lawyers are Matthew 5:17 on Christ's attitude towards the Old Law and Romans

2: 14–15 on the Law of Nature; thus, ‘medieval Christians recognized three divisions: the Law of Nature, the Law of Moses and the Law of Christ’ (p. 79), to which early Irish jurists added a fourth ‘Law of the Prophets (*recht fáide*)’ (p. 83). Evidence of the tetrad can be found in a series of Irish commentaries, under the influences of Jerome and Isidore (pp. 84–91). The author then gives a detailed analysis of the theological debates in Acts 15 and argues that they have provided a model of how biblical law in its different dispensations should be applied to resolving legal-theological disputes for the Irish jurists (pp. 91–97). Pelagian thoughts and the Ascetic Movement, she further suggests, contributed the idea of ‘natural goodness’ as the basis of the Law of Nature to the Irish (pp. 97–107). The next section, ‘*Collectio canonum Hibernensis*’ (pp. 107–120), points out how this collection established for the first time a set of procedural guidelines for canon jurists to consult legal authorities and reach decisions, which are analogous to those in Acts 15. In the discussion of the nature of judicial gatherings, the author states that ‘further evidence for the continuing existence of secular courts can be found in the eighth-century vernacular law tract *Uraicecht Becc*’, and cites from CIH 1592.8–20 (p. 115). Such evidence abounds, actually, for instance the Old Irish tract on court-procedure edited by Fergus Kelly in *Peritia* 5, where the identity and role of each attendant of court is well described. The passage from UB, on the other hand, may not be as useful as the author thinks, since the word *breth* ‘judgement’ can very often in early Irish law mean ‘legal provisions’ rather than ‘judicial verdict’, as is evinced by the titles of many law tracts which bear the word *bretha* ‘judgements’. It is also curious why the author does not cite here (though later on p. 141) the opening text from UB: *Cid i n-arragar breithemnus bérla fēni .nī. i fīr 7 dlged 7 aicned* ‘What is it in which the adjudication of the laymen’s lawsuit was bound? Not difficult, in truth and entitlement and nature’ (normalised from CIH 1590.1). The following paragraphs actually explain what are ‘truth’, ‘entitlement’, etc. and contradict some of the interpretation by the author here. The term *breth Fēne*, in the context where it is quoted as opposed to *breth filed* and *breth bérlae báin biaite*, should not be translated as ‘traditional lore’ (p. 116) but ‘judgement of the non-professional laymen / ordinary freemen’. *Breth flatha*, in the UB context, should mean something like ‘judgement in relation to a ruler’ rather than ‘royal law...promulgated on the authority of kings’ (p. 118). I regard UB as an important jurisprudential tract which holds the key to many ideological foundations of early Irish law; hopefully one day a more thorough analysis of it will emerge than what the present volume can afford. These considerations, however, do not affect the validity of the main arguments of this chapter, that the early Irish had gradually formed a unique way of application of their multifaceted, heterogeneous legal system (p. 120).

The next chapter is dedicated to the topic of ‘The Law of Nature’ (*recht aicnid*) (pp. 121–153). This concept ‘allowed secular interests to retain some aspects of the native legal system in exchange for their acceptance of an overall Christian

ideological framework' (p. 122). Apart from the 'natural goodness', the Irish also emphasised on the connection between the natural order and human behaviour, especially the automatic retribution by nature (p. 123). The author uses three texts to illustrate this point: *Collectio canonum Hibernensis*, Liber XXIV, cap. 4; *De duodecim abusivis saeculi*, cap. 9; and *Audacht Morainn*. In later sections, *Cáin Domnaig*, *Epistil Ísu* and the *Introduction* tract of *Senchas Már* are also brought into the comparison. This fresh treatment of a well-known theme provides another great example of the confluence of native and Christian ideologies. The opening lines of UB is quoted and analysed on pp. 141–143 in relation to the term 'nature (*aicned*)'. Again, this is not the place to hold a detailed philological and legal discussion, but I would translate *con-suiter aicned for logud oculus cocōrus* as: "nature" is based on remission and collaborative arrangement'. This seems to me to state the principle of equity: where stipulated law fails the natural justice, equity should kick in to remit what is overharsh and reach a mutually acceptable solution. All the concepts listed in this part of UB, I need to stress, can only be properly understood in reference to the 'paths' in *Cóic Conara Fuigill*. In any case, the Irish 'understood their pagan past as a period that all gentile nations experienced prior to conversion' (p. 145), and would have interpreted stories about pre-Christian heroes as exempla of *naturale bonum* among their pagan ancestors (p. 150), an idea which seems to enjoy 'wide currency in early Irish religious belief' (p. 151).

Chapter 5, 'Pseudo-history' (pp. 155–203), deals with this prominent genre in relation to how it shaped the imagination of early Irish law. The author argues that Irish pseudo-history is primarily aligned with a biblical, rather than a Roman-trojan framework, and has been widely exploited in legal circles to address a variety of ideological dilemmas (p. 160). By imagining themselves as gentiles with biblical lineage, who had uniquely received the Mosaic Law prior to the advent of Christianity, the medieval Irish could claim that their native law was not merely the Law of Nature but was infused with and enhanced by precepts drawn directly from the Law of Moses (pp. 164–165). This point has been persuasively shown by the author who resorts to the narrative about Caí Cáinbrethach and commentaries by Irenaeus, Pelagius and Alcuin. An analysis on the 'Pseudo-historical Prologue to the *Senchas Már*' ensues (pp. 169–203). The author proposes that Dubthach's judgement finds closest parallels to several chapters under *Collection canonum Hibernensis* Liber XXVI, *De sceleribus et uindictis eorum*. While the author focusses on the justification of capital punishment in these sources, I think there is something more in Dubthach's judgement. That judgement has opened up a new avenue of carrying out justice: the human arbitrators of justice are relieved from the dilemma of whether they should spare the culprit or punish him, because divine retribution and forgiveness occurred instantly, neither of which can be achieved under the available native law. The solution grafts the belief of spontaneous divine punishment, which is originally Irish, if we remember what the

author has shown in the previous chapter, onto Christian agents, in this case God. Again, this serves as an perfect example of the merge of native and imported legal ideologies. Therefore I do not agree with the author that Dubthach's judgement recommends 'ecclesiastically sanctioned executions' (p. 196) — although that is seen in Adomnán's *Lex Innocentium*. However, such an idealised solution cannot be relied on in real-life cases, and thus the later part of the Prologue returns to the accommodation of native Irish law under the Christian framework. As the author points out, the real matter of concern is still 'What law applies?' (p. 202). This chapter and the last may benefit from a dialogue with Daniel Watson's article 'A Law beyond Grace in the Prologue to Senchas Már' (2018).

The final chapters (pp. 211–294) cover the second theme of the book: the influence of Irish legal ideologies on Anglo-Saxon laws, in particular on the eighth-century Northumbrian legal texts and the biblical pseudo-history in the late ninth-century laws of King Alfred. These chapters develop further from the author's earlier studies on Anglo-Saxon laws. The Northumbrian texts under examination here, the *Dialogue of Ecgberht* and the *Legatine Capitulary of 786*, show a clear grouping of scriptural authorities into the Law of Christ, the Law of the Prophets, the Law of Moses, and the Law of nature, while being vague in the non-scriptural sources (p. 223). This feature is firstly shared with Alcuin's addition to the Carolingian *Admonitio Generalis* (pp. 224–228), and resonates secondly the hierarchy of the authorities of law in *Collectio canonum Hibernensis* Liber LXVI and XIX (pp. 229–231). The similarity is no coincidence, but, as the author argues, is due to the borrowing of the Irish method of invoking authorities into Northumbria, which has its own thriving legal culture (p. 240).

King Alfred perhaps faced a similar task as his contemporary Irish intellectuals, namely to conceptualise the Anglo-Saxon as a single *natio*, and to find a place in the sacred history for a recently converted gentile people (pp. 244–248). Unsurprisingly, pseudo-historical works were created and law was a central piece of that endeavour. The Prologue to the laws of Alfred laid out 'an ideologically loaded conceptualization of the relationship...between various kinds of law, including (1) the Law of Moses,... (2) the Law of Christ,...(3)all subsequent ecclesiastical legislation,...(4) the mostly traditional collection of statues that comprised the main body of his law code' (p. 256). Again, the shadow of Irish legal ideologies is long. Moreover, Alfred probably drew his Mosaic materials from manuscripts of *Collectio canonum Hibernensis* (p. 259), perhaps through Breton intermediates, and his focus on Exodus 20:1–23:12 may be inspired by Sulpicius Severus's *Chronicorum*, a text little known outside of Ireland (p. 261). Instead of framing the English as 'the new Chosen People', Alfred intended them as gentile converts who, like the Irish, were subject to the jurisdiction procedures listed in Acts 15 (p. 271). The Laws of Alfred, therefore, is redefined as 'ecclesiastical (or at least ecclesiastically sanctioned) legislation promulgated canonically by Anglo-Saxon jurisprudential bodies...which he

attributed the status of provincial synods' (p. 281). As for the pseudo-history, Chapter 10 reviews how the genealogies linked the English people to biblical lineages. Has this also been influenced by the similar practices in Ireland? The evidence is admittedly very thin, as the author points out.

In sum, this is a very well researched and finely articulated monograph. It raises many novel points and definitely will inspire many further discussions. The influence of early Irish law on neighbouring legal cultures, especially, is a field that still awaits exploration, and the author has done exemplary work which will hopefully be followed.

Fangzhe Qiu
University College Dublin